

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF STONE QUARRIES AND USE OF DUST AS SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS

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Abstract

Activation of stone dust generated as a result of reclamation of stone quarries on the Absheron Peninsula in order to improve the quality of asphalt concrete pavement

Keywords: activated dust, fatty acid, hydrophobicity, quarry, recultivation

Introduction

The Absheron peninsula, where two thirds of the industrial potential of the republic and one third of its population is concentrated, has undergone greater anthropogenic impact. This effect is increasing every year. Oil production, petrochemical, chemical and construction materials (stone, sand, gravel, cement) industries are particularly developed here, among the areas that have a harmful effect on the environment. Disruption of the natural complex is accelerated as a result of the dumping of construction industry waste into the environment. This creates conditions for the formation of irreversible processes in the geosystem. As a result, the natural accumulation of the soil cover affected by anthropogenic influence is disturbed and becomes unusable. For many years, due attention has not been paid attention to the restoration of lands disturbed for various reasons on the Absheron Peninsula and their return to use. For this reason, today the areas with old oil mines, sand and stone quarries have become so unusable that their recultivation requires a large amount of material, technical and financial resources, and the application of special technologies. Also, during the construction of residential and administrative buildings, industrial enterprises, stadiums, roads, water and gas pipelines and sewage systems, excavated rocks were thrown around, and fertile land became unusable. Erosion has also developed intensively in Absheron Peninsula soils. All types of erosion occur here. Due to the large number of windy days, wind erosion has developed more intensively here.

Strong winds cause serious damage to the environment by blowing moving sand, waste from the construction industry, and tiny particles from soil damaged by the impact of moving machinery.

The purpose of the study

The Absheron Peninsula is the driest area of the republic, and due to its natural conditions, it is not very suitable for human habitation, it is a semi-desert, its surface natural resources are very limited, but underground oil and gas resources, construction materials

(stone, sand, gravel, clay, etc.) is very rich with. The total area of disturbed lands due to the influence of the construction industry is 5344 ha. Most of the disturbed lands of this type are found in the territory of Garadagh district (3485 ha or 65.21%). Khazar region (812 ha) take the second place and Absheron region (493 ha) take the third place in terms of disturbance [1]. The reason for this is the existence of stone quarries in the territory of those regions. In order to minimize the spread of mineral dusts generated in stone quarries to the environment, as well as to use them efficiently, they can be used to improve the quality of asphalt pavement. Also, the development of this road construction is effective in the direction of extensive use of local road-building materials, secondary raw materials and industrial waste. [2]. The dust generated in the stone quarries in the Garadag and Guzdek areas, located on the Absheron Peninsula, is considered one of the main components of the asphalt-concrete coating.

The use of stone dust generated in stone quarries can reduce the negative impact on the environment. Also, high results can be achieved in the projects of preventing the creation of new stone quarries, speeding up the reclamation process, collecting stone dust and using it in asphalt pavement. One of the main ways of using mineral powders is to influence their surface with surfactants using physico-chemical technology. It was obtained by hydrolyzing fatty acid from natural oils as an activator.

This process is carried out in the following order. The process of separating fatty acids from triglycerides is carried out in a device equipped with a round-bottomed flask, a heater, a mechanical stirrer, and a thermometer. First, after the oil is heated to 65-70°C, 30% NaOH solution is added, and the temperature is raised to 90-95°C and the oil is hydrolyzed in an alkaline with stirring, and the sodium salt of fatty acids is obtained. At the next stage, the obtained salt treated with 30% HCl acid to separate the fatty acids, the acid washing 3 times and the excess alkali removed.

Then, the remaining water in the acid was evaporated and the fatty acids were separated. The acquisition of acid is determined by infrared spectroscopy analysis. [3].

The absorption bands of the IR spectrum of corn fatty acid were observed as follows:

2853, 2922 cm^{-1} - stretching vibrations of the C-H bond of CH_3 and CH_2 groups; 722, 1377, 1412, 1462 cm^{-1} - bending vibrations of the C-H bond of the CH_3 and CH_2 groups; 3009 cm^{-1} - stretching vibrations of $=\text{CH}_2$ groups; 936 cm^{-1} - bending vibrations, 3351 stretching vibrations

Table 1

Physical and chemical parameters of the synthesized fatty acids

The title of indicators	Device title	Method	title of the Sample		
			sunflower oil acid	C corn oil acid	Soy bean oil acid
freezing t temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Methodology	ГОСТ20287-91	+12	+15	+15
Refractive index, 20°C	AbbeMAT 500	Methodology	1,4693	1,4701	1,4693
Iodine number, g/100g	Methodology	ГОСТ 2070-82	78,05	67,05	67,83
Acid value mg KOH/1g	Methodology	ASTM D3242, ГОСТ 5985-79	164,83	235,33	261,25

The title of indicators	Device title	Method	Title of the Sample	
			cottonseed oil acid	palm oil acid
Freezing t temperature, °C	Mmethodology	ГОСТ20287-91	+15	+15
Refractive index, 20°C	Abbemat 500	Methodology	1,4790	1,4773
Iodine number, q/100q	Methodology	ГОСТ 2070-82	63,42	52,91
Acid value mg KOH/1g	Methodology	A STM D3242, ГОСТ 5985-79	167,27	150,31

*Hydrophobicity of mineral dust
a) unmodified dust b) modified dust*

A homogeneous mixture is slowly added to a chemical beaker filled with distilled water. The stone powder is ground in a grinding machine and mixed with the separated fatty acid to make it homogeneous. In order to test the hydrophobicity of the powder, the glass is moved back and forth once per second and kept still for 24 hours. If the distilled water becomes cloudy at the end of the process or if the powder does not settle to the bottom of the water, the powder is considered hydrophobic.

Conclusion

The conducted researches are devoted to the effective industrial application of the stone dusts that are not used as a result of the operation of stone quarries on the Absheron Peninsula. The use of stone dust in industrial asphalt pavement can help accelerate the reclamation of large stone quarries. Experiments conducted at the same time showed that the service life of the asphalt coating increases as a result of the mixing of the powders with the obtained fatty acids and the increase of

hydrophobicity. As a result, it is appropriate to use the generated dust in asphalt-concrete coating to realize the waste-free exploitation of stone quarries and at the same time to reduce the negative effects of new stone quarries on the environment.

References

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